

**GENDER EQUALITY AS A DRIVER OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT:
EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN****Fozilova Dilnavo Olim kizi**

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Abstract: This article discusses the issue of gender equality, its social, economic and legal aspects and its role in the development of society. The study analyzes the legislative framework of the Republic of Uzbekistan on ensuring gender equality, as well as gender policies and development programs promoted by international organizations. Also, through an analysis of the literature, the main causes of gender inequality are considered, in particular, the level of poverty of women, limited access to economic resources, insufficient recognition of their work and low participation in decision-making processes. In general, the article substantiates that ensuring gender equality is not only a legal issue, but also an important factor for the sustainable development of society.

Keywords: Gender equality, gender policy, women's rights, social justice, gender inequality, women's opportunities, poverty, gender approach, development, human rights.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается вопрос гендерного равенства, его социальные, экономические и правовые аспекты, а также его роль в развитии общества. В исследовании анализируется законодательная база Республики Узбекистан по обеспечению гендерного равенства, а также гендерная политика и программы развития, продвигаемые международными организациями. Кроме того, на основе анализа литературы рассматриваются основные причины гендерного неравенства, в частности, уровень бедности женщин, ограниченный доступ к экономическим ресурсам, недостаточное признание их труда и низкое участие в процессах принятия решений. В целом, статья обосновывает, что обеспечение гендерного равенства является не только правовым вопросом, но и важным фактором устойчивого развития общества.

Ключевые слова: Гендерное равенство, гендерная политика, права женщин, социальная справедливость, гендерное неравенство, возможности женщин, бедность, гендерный подход, развитие, права человека.

Zusammenfassung: Dieser Artikel befasst sich mit der Geschlechtergleichstellung, ihren sozialen, wirtschaftlichen und rechtlichen Aspekten sowie ihrer Rolle für die gesellschaftliche Entwicklung. Die Studie analysiert den Rechtsrahmen der Republik Usbekistan zur Gewährleistung der Geschlechtergleichstellung sowie die von internationalen Organisationen vorgelegten Programme und Strategien zur Geschlechterpolitik. Anhand einer Literaturanalyse werden zudem die Hauptursachen der Geschlechterungleichheit untersucht, insbesondere die Armut von Frauen, ihr eingeschränkter Zugang zu wirtschaftlichen Ressourcen, die unzureichende Anerkennung ihrer Arbeit und ihre geringe Teilhabe an Entscheidungsprozessen. Der Artikel belegt, dass die Gewährleistung der Geschlechtergleichstellung nicht nur eine rechtliche Frage, sondern auch ein wichtiger Faktor für die nachhaltige Entwicklung der

Gesellschaft ist.

Schlüsselwörter: Geschlechtergleichstellung, Geschlechterpolitik, Frauenrechte, soziale Gerechtigkeit, Geschlechterungleichheit, Chancengleichheit von Frauen, Armut, Genderansatz, Entwicklung, Menschenrechte

Introduction: After gaining independence, the Republic of Uzbekistan has made gender equality a priority of its state policy. The country is striving to fulfill its commitments under the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, in particular Goal 5 – “Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls” [1]. Article 58 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan states that all citizens, regardless of sex, are equal before the law and guarantees the non-admission of discrimination on the basis of gender. At the same time, various codes and laws in the national legislation, in particular the Law “On Guarantees of Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men”, serve to ensure equal rights of women in political, economic and social life [2].

Gender equality means that men and women have equal rights and opportunities in society. It requires the creation of fair conditions not only in the legal sense, but also in the social, economic and cultural spheres. President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev: “Today, women are addressed with a great appeal that every woman should not be an observer of democratic processes, but an active and proactive participant [3]. Imam Bukhari narrated from Abu Hurayrah (may Allah be pleased with him): “The Messenger of Allah (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) said: Treat women (kindly), for a woman was created from a rib. The crookedest part of a rib is at its top. If you try to straighten it, you will break it, and if you abandon it, it will remain crooked. So treat women (kindly)! So, in this way, the attitude towards women, issues of gender equality have been one of the issues that have not been developed and paid attention to in ancient times [4]. We can also see gender equality in the field of education. Ensuring gender equality in the field of education in Uzbekistan is one of the priorities of state policy. By widely introducing critical pedagogical approaches, it is possible to reduce gender stereotypes in the minds of young people, create equal opportunities, and increase gender justice [5].

Main part: Gender equality does not only mean legal and social equality between women and men, but also provides equal opportunities and justice for all gender groups. This equality should be reflected in education, employment, political activity, health care and family life. Many people consider women to be weaker than men. However, today our women and girls are occupying high positions in every field of sports, whether it is volleyball, football, boxing, track and field and weightlifting. Each of us must admit that today some men cannot do the tasks of women, but women can perfectly perform the tasks of men [6].

The factors influencing the development of gender policy are multifaceted and are closely related to historical traditions, cultural views, economic opportunities and the state of social institutions. Respect for women, family stability and traditional values play an important role in the unique social model of Uzbekistan. At the same time, these values are a complex process that must be combined with modern gender approaches and require continuous improvement of state policy. X especially, changes in the global labor market, the expansion of the digital economy, and the acceleration of urbanization are shaping new roles for women and renewing social demands on them. As a result, the state feels the need to strengthen institutional mechanisms to ensure gender equality [7].

Literature review: President Shavkat Mirziyoyev’s key quotes on gender equality,

women's rights and their role in society are as follows: "Human dignity and respect, first of all, begin with respect for our dear and holy mothers, our women" [8]. The central place in the literature is occupied by the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. O'RQ-562 "On Guarantees of Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men", adopted on September 2, 2019 [9, 10]. This law is significant not only for strengthening the legal framework for ensuring gender equality, but also for introducing such fundamental concepts as "gender", "temporary special measures on gender policy", "gender statistics", "gender legal expertise" and "gender audit" into national legislation [9]. J. Rawls's theory of justice is important in reconsidering the gender issue. The principle of "justice as equality" he put forward is aimed at protecting the interests of the most vulnerable in society, including women. According to Rawls' theory, social institutions should be organized in such a way that they provide equal opportunities [11].

Research methodology: This study was conducted on the basis of a comprehensive and systematic approach to studying gender equality issues. In particular, regulatory legal documents, in particular the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Law "On Guarantees of Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men", were analyzed, the basic principles, legal guarantees established in them and their practical significance were highlighted. Also, national and foreign scientific literature was studied and, by comparing them, the main theoretical views, approaches and scientific concepts related to gender equality were summarized. During the study, special attention was paid to determining the relationship between gender policy and social and economic factors. In this process, logical analysis, induction and deduction methods were used to identify existing problems and formulate sound scientific conclusions on their solution.

Analysis and Results: The analysis shows that gender inequality remains a persistent global issue despite the existence of international legal frameworks and development commitments. According to findings, approximately one billion women live below the poverty line, which is twice as many as men in the same condition. This clearly indicates a significant gender gap in poverty distribution.

Women generally work longer hours than men, yet a large part of their work, such as childcare and household responsibilities, remains unpaid and unrecognized. In addition, women have less access to land and other productive resources and are less involved in political and community decision-making processes. This limits their opportunities for economic and social development.

The results also reveal that development programs which ignore gender relations are less effective and fail to improve the living conditions of women and girls. In contrast, integrating a gender-sensitive approach into development policies significantly improves outcomes. For example, women reinvest about 90 percent of their income into their families and communities, while men reinvest only 30–40 percent, which shows the strong impact of empowering women on poverty reduction and social welfare.

Furthermore, practical experiences from development projects demonstrate that applying gender analysis helps to identify real needs, reduce inequalities, and design more effective and inclusive interventions. Therefore, gender mainstreaming plays a crucial role not only in achieving equality but also in enhancing the overall effectiveness of development cooperation.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, gender equality is one of the key factors for sustainable social development. Although significant legal and institutional frameworks have been established in Uzbekistan, certain issues related to gender inequality still persist in practice. In particular, women's access to economic resources, their participation in decision-making processes, and their level of social activity remain lower compared to men. The analysis shows that social and economic programs implemented without considering gender factors often fail to achieve the expected results. In contrast, applying a gender-sensitive approach, expanding women's opportunities, and increasing their participation can contribute not only to achieving gender equality but also to improving overall societal well-being. Notably, women tend to allocate a larger share of their income to their families and communities, which plays an important role in development. Therefore, it is essential not only to improve legal frameworks but also to widely integrate a gender perspective into education, the economy, and social sectors. This will serve as a crucial factor in ensuring justice, equal opportunities, and sustainable development in society.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati

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